

Rwanda: What Drives the Nation in International Trade?

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ABSTRACT

The authors investigated whether Rwanda as a member of the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) has comparative advantage in the products that it exports. The results have shown that Rwanda has revealed comparative advantage in 294 product lines. Pyrethrum, roots containing rotenone extracts has the highest index of 12139.35. The authors have concluded that Rwanda has comparative advantage and just needs to increase their production and promote them.

KEY WORDS: Comparative advantage, external trade, export promotion, marketing, Rwanda

INTRODUCTION

Rwanda is a member of the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA). The authors are citizens of COMESA hence their interest in macroeconomic indicators of Rwanda. One of the most important indicators that can reveal the extent of Rwanda's participation in intra-COMESA trade and in the global trade is competitiveness of its exports. This article investigates the comparative advantage of Rwanda in international trade.

BACKGROUND

Rwanda was ruled by the German and became part of the German East Africa in the late 19th Century. The control was later on passed on to the Belgians after World War I. The Belgian colonial government for the next four decades gave preferences to Tutsis over the Hutus. The Hutus who constituted 85% of the population were forced as labourers under the supervision of minority. In 1959, the Hutus revolted against Tutsi monarchy. The revolt led Tutsis into exile in neighboring countries. The Tutsis fled again in 1969 and 1972 and were not permitted to return to Rwanda (Boudreaux, 2007).

In the 1990s, exile Tutsis under the umbrella of the Rwanda Patriotic Front (RPF) invaded Rwanda. The invasion however did not succeed. The Hutu government of Juvenal Habyarimana amended the Constitution and integrated RPF into the national army under the power sharing agreement reached with Tutsis in Arusha, Tanzania. In 1994, the President was killed while

returning from Tanzania by elements of Hutu hard liners (extremist) who were not in favour of the implementation of the peace accord. Rwandan Armed Forces and the Hutu Interahamwe militia and others began to kill innocent Tutsi civilians and by the time RPF managed to stop the killing, about 1 million people had been killed. The Hutu government fled into exile but had been held accountable to genocide (Boudreaux, 2007). Rwanda went through a period of civil war which culminated in the 1994 genocide (McDonough, 2008).

Rwanda after peace returned has been engaging its economy to prosperity. According to Rwanda's Vision 2020 Plan, it has very ambitious objectives for growth which will need the economy to expand seventy fold. However, taking into account what the country has gone through, the economy needs to expand by 250% between 2010 to 2020 for it to increase its output per capita from US\$550 to US\$900. Rwanda's exports have expanded significantly from US\$367 million in 2009 to US\$454 million in 2010. This figure includes receipts from tourism. However, imports in Rwanda have increased much more than exports. Imports increased from US\$282 million in 2003 to US\$1.3 billion in 2010 (Government of Rwanda, 2011).

Rwanda has come up with priority sectors in its National Export Strategy in the short and medium terms. These include sectors such as tea, coffee, tourism and mining. In its long term, the National Export Strategy intends to support all sectors through the cross cutting issues such as human capital development, finance and investment, infrastructure, monetary and fiscal policy, business

environment, encouraging innovations and economic diversification, trade facilitation and promotion, gender equality, youth, rural and environmental areas (Government of Rwanda, 2011). In order for Rwanda to achieve the objectives spelled out in its National Export Strategy the country need to demonstrate that it has some comparative advantage.

COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE

According to Case and Fair (2002) the principle of comparative advantage as propagated by David Ricardo was used to advance argument against the corn laws in his time. The principle of comparative advantage states that specialization and free trade ensures gain to all countries involved in trade (wages would increase) despite the fact that some countries may be absolutely inefficient. David Ricardo further argued that even though some nations may possess absolute advantage in producing both goods, specialization and trade all the time are mutually beneficial. The trading partners are required to specialize in the products in which they have comparative advantage hence their combined output becomes more efficient as they maximize resource allocation. In a 2 country and 2 goods model, a country is said to have comparative advantage if say tea production only if its opportunity cost, in relation to sugar is lower than the other trading partner. Mzumara (2006) highlights later works on comparative advantage citing Swedish economists namely Hecksher and Ohlin. The two wrote at different times but later it was discovered they wrote on the same thing. They did not invalidate the principle of comparative advantage as did David Ricardo to Adam Smith's absolute advantage instead they extended it. According to them comparative

advantage is determined by international differences in factor endowment. The endowments of labour and capital means that a country with abundant labour resources will produce goods which use labour resources most intensively. Then in this case, it will import those products which use scarce factor in this case capital less intensively. This will set in specialization by countries.

EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE OF COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGE

Mirzaei et al (2004) investigated whether Iran had comparative advantage in the eggs which it exports to the Middle East region. The study used the revealed comparative advantage (RCA) to measure comparative advantage. The study found that Iran had no comparative advantage in the eggs it exported to the Middle East region. Mzumara (2011a) used the RCA to measure the competitiveness of Zimbabwe. The results revealed that Zimbabwe had comparative advantage. Mzumara (2011b) applied the RCA technique when the study investigated whether Mozambique had comparative advantage. The results showed that Mozambique had $RCA \geq 1$ in 222 product lines. The study concluded that Mozambique had comparative advantage. Shinyekwa and Othieno (2011) investigated using RCA whether Uganda had comparative advantage. The study found out that Uganda had comparative advantage in very limited range of products. Mzumara (2012) using harmonized 6-digit level data and RCA technique investigated whether Botswana is a mono-diamond economy. The study found out that Botswana has comparative advantage in 244 product lines and concluded that Botswana is not a mono-diamond economy.

METHODOLOGY

This paper has used Balassa (1965) Revealed Comparative Advantage RCA. Although there are a number of methods which use indices, this paper chose RCA as Wu and Chen (2004) put it

that the index can be employed to represent both the relative competitiveness of the same product in various countries and the relative competitiveness of various products within the same country. They strongly justify the method as the most useful tool in a competitive market economy to demonstrate comparative advantage as revealed in export composition. This is due to its consistence with comparative advantage which is based on the particular nation's economy factor endowment and operates along with economic development. Balassa (1965) index takes the form of:

$$RCA = \left(\frac{X_{i,j}}{X_{W,j}} \right) / \left(\frac{X_{i,tot}}{X_{W,tot}} \right)$$

With:

RCA denoting Revealed Comparative Advantage;

$X_{i,j}$ denoting country i 's exports of product j ;

$X_{i,tot}$ denoting country i 's total exports;

$X_{w,j}$ denoting the world's (all countries) export of product j ; and

$X_{w,tot}$ denoting total exports in the world.

An RCA of equal and greater than 1 demonstrates that the country has revealed comparative advantage. In other words, the exporting nation is relatively specialized in producing and exporting the product line under consideration. An RCA of less than 1 demonstrates that a country has no revealed comparative advantage and is not specialized in the product line (Balassa, 1965; Krugell & Matthee, 2009).

Data on exports for Rwanda and for the world was obtained from International Trade Centre (ITC)'s Trademap based in Geneva, Switzerland for 2007, 2008 and 2009. An RCA was computed for every product separately for 2007, 2008 and 2009 then an average RCA for the three years was computed which was used either to reject as lack of comparative advantage or accepting that Rwanda possesses a comparative advantage in a particular product. Data for Rwanda for 2010 was not available.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Rwanda was found to have an $RCA \geq 1$ in 294 products lines. This shows that Rwanda has revealed comparative advantage in those product lines hence is specialized in their production. Table 1 shows top 25 products in which Rwanda has comparative advantage.

Table 1: Top 25 products in which Rwanda has comparative advantage

Product code	Product description	2007 RCA	2008 RCA	2009 RCA	Average RCA
130214	Pyrethrum, roots containing rotenone, extracts	36418.05	0	0	12139.35
260900	Tin ores concentrates	11812.05	8566.817	5593.504	8657.456
261590	Niobium, tantalum and vanadium ores and concentrates	6576.989	7697.708	3994.586	6089.761
261100	Tungsten ores and concentrates	6357.195	2563.295	1944.375	3621.621

410229	Sheep or lamb skins, raw, except pickled, no wool	4479.299	1491.722	0	1990.34
261790	Ores and concentrates	1605.841	781.3697	2312.289	1566.5
860712	Railways & tramway bogies & bissel-bogies, non driving	1502.645	737.9202	1078.739	1106.435
090240	Tea, black (fermented or partly) in packages >3kg	497.2248	1591.827	1217.597	1102.216
860120	Railway locomotives powered by electric accumulators	1353.131	840.0047	558.6073	917.2476
930119	Artillery weapons (eg guns, hotwitzer & mortars other than self propelling	1026.733	928.5612	513.7865	823.0269
853010	Electric signal, safety & traffic controls, railway	1158.615	542.9618	695.6309	799.0692
880220	Fixed wing aircraft, unladen weight <2 000kg	540.8686	301.1306	905.6178	582.539
090230	Tea, black (fermented or partly) in packages <3kg	868.8324	182.7622	19.669	357.0879
410310	Goat or kid hides and skins, raw	833.4285	0	0	277.8095
860500	Railway passenger and special purpose	406.2805	205.3351	170.3479	260.6545

	coaches				
847690	Parts of automatic goods-vending machinery	342.1085	163.4456	276.1034	260.5525
846040	Honing or lapping machines	346.647	147.3181	278.1002	257.3551
070820	Beans, shelled or unshelled, fresh or chilled	100.00501	606.9702	24.09369	243.7047
880212	Helicopters of an unladen weight >2000kg	332.5131	165.1793	231.3873	243.7047
901110	Stereoscopic microscopes	0	0	625.3767	208.4589
845811	Horizontal numerically controlled metal work lathes	218.5594	107.9211	281.9578	202.8128
090190	Coffee husks and skins	9.345917	231.6313	266.6611	169.2128
860400	Railway maintenance of-way service vehicles	279.2236	115.3721	112.8927	169.1628
900719	Cinematographic cameras for film >16mm wide	424.6357	12.6485	32.53584	156.6076
851780	Electric apparatus for line	461.8167	0	0	153.9389
090111	Coffee, not roasted, not decaffeinated	188.5142	136.9157	112.3168	145.9156
848050	Moulds for glass	178.1205	81.83363	116.2203	125.2582
721011	Flat rolled iron or non-alloy steel, coated	85.47762	269.148	0	118.2055

	with tin w>600mm, t>0.5				
860721	Air brakes parts for railway rolling stock	155.6283	66.1949	91.72237	104.5152
410692	Tanned/crust hides & skins, without wool/hair on, in the dry state	0	0	305.1899	101.73

Source: Computed using data obtained from Trademap (2013).

Apasyrethrum, roots containing rotenone extracts has the highest index of 12139.35. It is followed by tin ores concentrates with index of 8657.5. The third position is occupied by niobium, tantalum and vanadium ore concentrates. These have an index of 6089.8. The fourth position is occupied by tungsten ores and concentrates with an index of 1990.3. Ores and concentrates occupy the sixth position with an index of 1566.5. Amongst the composition, there are primary products, such as minerals, agricultural products and some manufactured products.

These results conform to the principle of comparative advantage that any given country may have some comparative advantage in some of the products it produces and exports. There is evidence that Rwanda has the comparative advantage in line with the proposition of the theory as advanced by Ricardo and then extended by Heckscher and Ohlin. This is sufficient evidence that Rwanda is gaining in engaging in intra-COMESA trade. For the 294 products in which Rwanda has comparative advantage that the country is competitive over other producers in the world market.

The results are also consistent with the findings in the other past studies done by Mzumara (2011a;2011b), Shinyekwa and Otieno (2011) and Mzumara (2012). However, the results are not consistent with the results of Mirzaei et al (2004). This is mainly due to the fact that Mirzaei et al study investigated whether Iran had comparative advantage in a single product namely eggs while this study investigated all the products that Rwanda exports and indeed the country was found to have comparative advantage in 294 product lines while

in Mirzaei et al the hypothesis was rejected Iran had no comparative advantage in the eggs.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper's results have shown that there is sufficient evidence that Rwanda has comparative advantage in the 294 product lines. There is also sufficient evidence that Rwanda is benefiting in engaging in trade both in the context of regional trade e.g. intra-COMESA as well as global trade under the auspices of the World Trade Organization (WTO). It is recommended that Rwanda should find ways of increasing the production of the products in which it has demonstrated competency through its production capabilities. It is further recommended that it strengthens its export promotion, export development and international marketing. These three functions play an important role in global markets.

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